

Alternative course programs for students who were not able to meet the requirements in Accountancy at St. Dominic College of Asia

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Abstract

This research was formulated to determine the alternative course programs for students who were not able to meet the requirements in accountancy in St. Dominic College of Asia, specifically to why students shift to other programs. The descriptive research design was used in this study. The researcher gathered data from forty-two (42) respondents using a survey questionnaire. BS Accounting Technology has the highest respondents with 34 or 81% of the students. Quota grade becomes the major factor for students who shifted to other programs. Other students also transferred from St. Dominic College of Asia to another school based on various factors. It is recommended that educators conduct activities that could be beneficial to the studies of accounting students. Accounting educators could provide a student-centered environment to allow students to develop their skills and be professionally competitive. More so, the researcher recommends guiding and giving advice to the students who want to shift to other courses.

Keywords: Quota grade; Level of difficulty; Financial problem; Alternative course program; Accountancy.

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Introduction

To give further knowledge about the Accountancy course, the Bachelor of Science in Accountancy is a five-year professional degree program of accounting education. It is an ideal career for incoming college students because it offers great career opportunities starting at entry-level jobs to more advanced positions. The students need not only the with basic and advanced knowledge of accounting concepts, principles, and procedures, but also the program should need to provide a foundation of professional knowledge, skills, values, ethics and attitudes that enable them to continue to adapt throughout their profession. To be a competent professional accountant, it is necessary to develop strong knowledge, foundation, and skills necessary with appropriate professional skepticism.

Bachelor of Science in Accountancy composed of subjects in the Certified Public Accounting Licensure Exam (CPALE) such as auditing theories and problems, management advisory services, financial accounting and reporting (FAR), advanced financial accounting and reporting (AFAR), regulatory framework for business transactions (RFBT), and taxation. It prepares the students for entry into the four (4) major fields in accountancy that include public practice, commerce and industry, government, and education. They must pass the Certified Public Accountant Licensure Examination to practice their chosen profession. However, having the Certified Public Accountant (CPA) title is not easy to achieve. Not everyone who took this course will successfully march in the end with the same course taken.

Bachelor of Science in Accountancy is one of the most difficult major courses both locally and internationally. Aside from that, Certified Public Accountant Licensure Examination (CPALE) is one of

the hardest board examinations in the world. The struggles you would experience as an undergraduate are undeniably hard. It has been said that college is the hardest part of being a student, and it becomes tougher if one chooses to pursue the accountancy profession. Many accountancy students failed and shifted to other courses because of the retention policy implemented in every school (Hopper, 2013).

According to Commission on Higher Education (CHED), the standards of admission to the Accountancy program should be sufficiently demanding and rigorous (Licuanan, 2017). St. Dominic College of Asia has the admission and retention policy for the Bachelor of Science in Accountancy. At St. Dominic College of Asia, the retention policy in the Bachelor of Science in Accountancy program is that the students are obliged to maintain a grade of at least 2.25 or its equivalent of eighty-five percent (83%) or higher in their accounting-related or professional subjects and a grade of 2.5 or equivalent to eighty percent (80%) in the general education subjects, and they need to pass the qualifying exam or the Dean Assessment Test (DAT) for them to continue the accountancy program.

St. Dominic College of Asia Certified Public Accountant Board Exam Passers performance for the last three years: October 2019 was 50% and in May 2019 0%; October 2018 - 33.33%, May 2018 - 0%, and October 2017 - 0% and May 2017 - 0%. Indeed, a Bachelor of Science in Accountancy is considered a very difficult course; the course needs a combination of full knowledge, skills, and the right behavior to succeed. The preparation is very crucial to achieving the goal of finishing the course and the review up to taking the board exam. That is why many of the students are shifting courses because of the difficulty of the accounting course. They also have alternative courses to take, like Bachelor of Science in Business Administration majoring in Management Accounting (BSBA-MA), Marketing Management, Operations Management (BSBA-OM), and Financial Management since accounting is related to business. Switching programs in college when you have already started means another transition phase to prepare for. Deciding to shift for a variety of reasons can be disheartening and complicated as picking a program could be.

In line with this, this study aims to find out why students did not pursue to stay in Accountancy course and what alternative programs should they take that is still related to the course. The outcome of the study would be useful to the students who will take the Accountancy program, as it will give information about whether they will take the program or not. It will give information on what alternative programs most students chose after not meeting the requirements of the program.

Statement of the Problem

The study aims to identify the alternative programs for students who did not meet the requirements for Accountancy. It would also determine the factors which made the students shift courses and how to lessen the number of students shifting to other courses.

1. What is the profile of the students in terms of?
 - 1.1 Gender
 - 1.2 Age
 - 1.3 Course upon graduation from college
2. What are the factors why students shift programs?
3. What alternative programs did the students choose to take?

Related Studies

Making decisions implies that we have choices that need to be considered in pursuing our careers; we want to identify as many alternatives as possible, but we choose the one that best fits with our goals, objectives, desires, values, and so on (Hammond et al., 2015).

According to Khalid and Rauf (2020), one of the major factors that have been affecting college students to graduate earlier is the shifting of courses of the college student, especially after two years of experience of their studies. Shifting is a way for college students to change their chosen program to another that may be caused by many incompatibilities of the student to compete in that specific chosen program. According to the Office of the University Registrar of De La Salle University (DLSU), “shifting refers to a transfer from one program to another of the same level. A level may refer to baccalaureate, masters, doctoral, or diploma/certificate.” In some college students’ perspective about shifting courses, shifting courses was caused by rejection of the problems of the student in that specific program. Shifting of course is a way for college students to change their chosen program to another that may have been caused by many incompatibilities to compete in that specific program. Choosing to pursue a course makes more difficult. Even the brightest student fails in class sometimes. On the other hand, it is unhealthy to force a student into something that they are not happy with. It will only result in disappointments and regrets in the future.

Due to accounting and finance, courses are the combination of heavily theoretical and quantitative aspects; most students believe that these courses are difficult. As a result, most students have withdrawn from the course because their quality does not match the skills that were required by these courses. In a study conducted by Uyar et al. (2011), it shows that the difficulty of the course has no significant effect on students' choice of accounting. Switching major programs will result in additional courses, which may require a student to take summer courses or stay an extra semester to catch up.

While it may seem undesirable to extend your college career, in the end, it is not a big deal. Staying an extra semester and graduating with the degree one desires is better than second-guessing the career path immediately after graduation. One is likely to perform better if it is something you enjoy, and there will be less confusion and self-doubt when you are figuring out what type of job you would like to do once you finish college.

College students’ backgrounds—more especially, the financial situation of their parents—have a significant impact on their financial situations. Every student starts with family income, and despite the degree of present reliance on parental funds, this history influences college students’ financial attitudes and actions (Graves & Savage, 2015; Widener, 2017). The foundation of any ability or skill set is arguably the relevant knowledge and understanding necessary to perform such tasks. Financial literacy is certainly an influence on money decisions; the degree to which college students understand money is also a representation of financial situations. Research indicates that most people agree that financial literacy is a significant determinant of quality of life and future decision-making (Thomas & Subhashree, 2020). Despite this, college students tend to score very low on tests of financial knowledge (Beierlein & Neverett, 2013; Henager & Cole, 2016).

The beginning of online education has made it possible for students with busy lives and limited flexibility to obtain a quality education. Web-based instruction has rendered it feasible to provide classes globally using a single Internet connection, in contrast to traditional classroom instruction (Paul & Jefferson, 2019). Although it boasts several advantages over traditional education, online instruction still has its drawbacks, including limited sources. It shows that many students are choosing to complete their degrees online. However, studying as accounting students is a different case. The face-to-face was already a struggle for many of us; if we are having a hard time understanding an accounting subject, what more would have happened if we studied online with a buffering internet connection? The quality of learning will depend on the students most of the time. The disturbance while studying will probably occur depending on your environment, and it will have a big impact on the student's academic performance that will soon lead to the decision to shift course.

Most colleges and universities face challenges and stability during college in time with the student’s selection of course. This phenomenon seems global throughout educational institutions. Students rush to classes that appear to be of interest to them, yet they frequently switch to other classes at other times. From the point of view of development, individuals given a longer and healthier life span may change over time and find out that an earlier occupational choice no longer satisfies them.

Viewed from this perspective, a choice made in adolescence may be less important than the ability to make good decisions. Flexibility and willingness to change may be as critical as the ability to commit oneself to a goal; thus, shifting courses is no exemption. With the exemption of certain schools and certain courses, freshmen and sophomores usually take general introductory courses, while juniors and seniors are concentrating on academic subjects. However, what causes shifting from one course to another would obviously mean that several failures might be responsible for a person's choice. It also examines those factors that lead to differences in academic performance based on gender through human capital theory. Academic performance increases individual productivity, suggesting that females are more valuable in the labor market than males (Castagnetti & Rosti, 2009). Thus, the learning process is like production. Student academic grades, therefore, can be correlated as a measure of how a different factor affects grades. Some studies have confirmed the positive relationship between gender and college students' academic performance (Bazelais et al., 2016; Eriksson et al., 2020; Rainey et al., 2018; Voyer & Voyer, 2014).

The positive attitude toward accounting with effective study habits might lead to higher grades and later passing the board examination. Freshmen should also have passion, because no matter how effective other factors are, what will make them successful in the field of accounting is their love for the said field. Further, students are weak in practical accounting, and this is attributed to a lack of hands-on experience in the real-life aspect of accounting (Ballada-Tan, 2014).

Retention policy is a set of guidelines to fully assess students in their ability to finish the course. Fowler and Luna (2009) defined retention in educational settings as "students' continued study until successful completion." The primary objective of retention policy is to provide a means for students to acquire the knowledge, proficiency, and intellectual abilities to provide services of the minimum scope and quality which the public needs and has a right to expect from entry level professional accountant, to in order to challenge and improve the performance of accountancy students, and the capacity to grow and develop into fully qualified professional accountant able to function in a global economy.

In other students' points of view, all accountancy students are intelligent and skilled in analysis and problem solving but having the retention policy make it harder for all the BSA students. Many failed and chose to shift to another course or program because of the retention policy. Retention policies in Accountancy focus on limiting the number of times a student can repeat a course and those that determine how many times a student can withdraw from a course. Most universities and colleges oblige students to maintain their grades at least 2.00, equivalent to eighty-five percent (85%), or higher in the accounting-related or professional subjects.

Students in St. Dominic College of Asia are obliged to maintain their grades at least 2.25 or equivalent to eighty-five percent (83%) or higher in their accounting-related or professional subjects, and a grade of 2.5 or equivalent to eighty percent (80%) in the general education subjects, and they need to pass the qualifying exam or the Dean's Assessment Test (DAT) for them to continue the accountancy program. The quality of students' performance remains a top priority for educators. Educators, trainers, and researchers have long been interested in exploring variables contributing effectively to the quality of performance of learners. These variables are inside and outside of school that affect students' quality of academic achievement. These factors may be classified as student factors, family factors, school factors, and peer factors (Crosnoe et al., 2004).

Olamide and Oluwaiye (2013) observed that while students aim at such prestigious occupations when still in secondary school, it has not been possible for many to achieve their aims for one reason or the other. Such reasons often include among others; poor academic performance, poor choice of subjects for the school certificate examination, lack of financial support to pursue their education which makes it impossible for such boys and girls to get their required training that would qualify them for the jobs of their choice. The business environment has always affected the purpose of accounting education, as well as the demand and supply of accountants (Al-Hattani, 2021; Herbert et al., 2021; Pincus et al., 2017). All these factors play an important role in determining what should be taught to accounting students.

Flood and Wilson (2008) emphasized that accounting education must foster students' understanding of the principles and concepts that underpin accounting and business practices. In any case, if the students did not meet the requirements and had no choice but to shift course, a business course would be advisable for them to take because of its relation to accountancy. Typically offered as a Bachelor of Science in Accounting Information System, a four-year degree in accounting is a highly specialized program that prepares graduates to work in varied capacities within the accounting industry. This level of education may be ideal for students who are not looking to become certified public accountants (CPA), as the certification requires additional coursework at the graduate level. Graduates of an accounting degree program will have an in-depth and holistic knowledge of the business cycle and the accounting principles governing responsible practices. Specific skills include preparing financial statements and tax documents, internal auditing, financial advisement, and more broad-based skills in organizational management and evaluation of a company's overall effectiveness.

Methodology

The descriptive research design was used in this study. The respondents of the study are Bachelor of Science in Accountancy students at St. Dominic College of Asia, who shifted to another program. The population is determined by getting the total number of shifters for the last five school years from 2016 to 2021. Unfortunately, the researchers were not able to get the exact number of students that shifted to another program for the last five school years. Based on the gathered information, the researcher can find 50 respondents who were previously accountancy students who shifted to other courses. However, only 42 respondents returned the questionnaire.

The researcher conducted a survey by using an online survey questionnaire through Google Forms as it is a flexible form and survey development interface with built-in reporting. The survey is conducted by all the students who shifted programs from Bachelor of Science in Accountancy. The survey questionnaire is structured in such a way that the respondents will be able to answer it easily. Percentage was used to determine the highest and the lowest points of each question in the survey.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents (n=42)

Category	Variables	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	7	17%
	Female	35	83%
Age	Below 21	2	5%
	21-25	36	86%
	Over 30	4	9%
Course upon Graduation on College	Accounting Technology	34	80.95%
	Information Technology	2	4.765%
	BS Mathematics	1	2.38%
	Hospitality Management	2	4.765%
	Marine Electrical	1	2.38%
	Secretarial Science	1	2.38%
	Computer Science	1	2.38%

Table 1 shows that 7 or 17% of respondents are males and the remaining 35 or 83% are females. When grouped according to age, there are 5% or 2 respondents below who are 21 years old; ages 21 to 25 years old, which is equivalent to 36 or 86% of total respondents; and none of the respondents are 26 to 30 years old. Lastly, over 30 years old answered with a total of 4 respondents, or 9%.

When grouped according to the graduate course, out of 42 respondents, there are 34 respondents, or equivalent to 80.95% had shifted to BS Accounting Technology; BS Information Technology and BS Hospitality Management both have two respondents which equivalents to 4.77% respectively. The remaining 9.52%, which is equivalent to four respondents, each answered BS Mathematics, Marine Electrical Engineering, Secretarial Science, and Computer Science as their respective taken courses. This means that these students transferred from St. Dominic College of Asia to another school.

Table 2. Respondents' reasons why they shift to other programs (n=42)

	Reasons	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1.	Time / Longevity	1	2%
2.	Student Habit	1	2%
3.	Level of Difficulty	8	19%
4.	Pressure	4	10%
5.	Financial Problem	5	12%
6.	Quota Grade	23	55%

Table 2 illustrates the factors that influence BS Accountancy students to shift courses. Out of the 42 responses received, most of them mentioned quota grade as their reason why they shifted courses, with 23 or 55% of respondents. Eight respondents mentioned level of difficulty as the reason they shifted, composing 19% of the total responses received. Then, financial problems are viewed by 5 or 12% of respondents as the reason why they shifted to other courses. Four (4) or 10% of the respondents answered pressure, and lastly, time or longevity of the program and student habits have 1 or 2% of the responses, respectively.

This study is conducted to determine other possible courses available for students at St. Dominic College of Asia. The researchers intend to find the answers to the statement of the problem, which includes the demographic profile of the respondents and factors why students shift to other programs. Most of the respondents are females, with 35 respondents compared to seven (7) male respondents. In a human capital theory, academic performance increases individual productivity, suggesting that females are more valuable in the labor market than males. Thus, the learning process is like production. Student academic grades, therefore, can be correlated as a measure of how different factors affect grades.

As to factors why accountancy students shift to other programs, the highest is quota grade as their major reason why they shifted to other courses, with 23 respondents. A study conducted by Owusu et al. (2019) shows that the difficulty of the course has a significant negative effect on students' choice of accounting. The quota grade that is part of the retention policy in school is the major factor on why students choose to end their career as an accountant and shift to another program or career.

Conclusions

Most students shift to another course because they cannot keep the minimum grade quota required to continue. This shows that if students cannot meet the demand of the course they enrolled in, they just shift to another course. Students realize that grades matter a lot, and it is the guiding rule whether to continue or not with the enrolled course. Students decide early so they can avoid wasting time finishing a very challenging course. They came up with the decision to stop and accept that the course was not for them. Students managed to change courses or shift to other programs just to finish their college degrees. No one can push students to proceed if they feel that the course is not for them. If students have a weak foundation in basic accounting courses, they will likely suffer if they reach the major courses in accountancy that are more complicated. A very good foundation to understand accounting better is essential for students to pursue in passing the board exam. Quota grades should continue to be maintained in the accountancy program to help students gauge their full potential, whether to continue the course, and provide alternative courses for advancement.

However, in shifting to another program, most students prefer Accounting Technology, which is obviously the closest program to Accountancy. Other programs that become an alternative to BS Accountancy are BS Information Technology, BS Mathematics, Marine Electrical, Secretarial Science, and Computer Science. This shows that most students who take accountancy have the intelligence to analyze data and solve problems. So, whatever the alternative course that the students will take in case of failing in accountancy, they can still guarantee immediate employment. According to Debara (2021), problem-solving skills are critical for any career path that, regardless of the job and its location, one will still face big and small problems all the time. So, if one wants to succeed in his or her career, being able to effectively analyze and solve problems is a must. If one is looking for a job, showcasing problem-solving skills can help one land a dream job.

Recommendations

Based on the result, quota grade is the top reason why most students shift to other programs, and their taken course is BS Accounting Technology. Hence, for the students, it is recommended to keep their passion burning; this research is made for them to have other options if things do not work out, as they should be. They can still be in line with accounting by shifting to BS Accounting Technology, and if their mind and body are all ready to take a chance again on their goal to be a CPA, then they can reach the BS in Accountancy course. As students, they must accept quota grades are just part of a retention policy, which is a motivational tool to improve their studies. If ever their hard work is not enough for them to pass the quota grade, they need to learn how to let go of the things that may not be for us. However, they should keep their heads up and enjoy the process of life.

To the institution, activities must be conducted that could be beneficial to the accounting students. Accounting educators could provide a student-centered environment to allow students to develop their skills and be professionally competitive. Instructors should provide professional advice to the students who want to shift to other courses. Accounting professors, through their ideas and knowledge, should give their best in helping and training the students to develop and to attain their goal and give them hope to finish their studies even if it is not the path that they chose first. As for future researchers, they should try to dig deeper and explore other possible alternative programs. The scope of this study is limited to only one professional school, so future researchers could add broader sources and scope to obtain more significant data.

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